

List of skills of the ETF and their definitions.

Id Group	Skill group	Id Skill	Skill	Description
A			self-management	get work done while operating alone, with little supervision; monitor and evaluate own performance; be aware of own strengths / weaknesses
			adaptability	demonstrate openness to change when faced with changing demands and circumstances; adjust plans, goals, behaviours and actions to effectively and successfully cope with change; demonstrate flexibility when coping with various circumstances
			organisation	schedule and optimise activities and available resources; monitor and evaluate progress; set priorities; coordinate work to accomplish an objective; break down tasks into smaller components and delegate when possible
			personal development	understand own learning needs to progress in life, work and study; set goals to realise and maximise own potential; take control of own personal growth; embrace new experiences and learn from them; engage in continuous learning to develop, maintain and improve skills and knowledge; demonstrate a growing autonomy in acquiring knowledge, know-how and new behaviours
			positive attitude	display energy, enthusiasm, passion, optimism and positive thinking; keep up the good spirit and believe in oneself and others, even in challenging situations
			self-control	regulate own emotions, thoughts, and behaviours in the face of temptations and impulses; control impulse; stop and think before acting; manage feelings by thinking about goals to keep going when faced with upsetting and unexpected circumstances; control body movements
B			accountability	perform, complete assigned tasks in a goal-oriented manner; take ownership; accept liability for professional decisions, involving self or others; realise that choices and actions have positive and negative consequences; recognise limits to autonomy; understand when to seek help
			customer focus	aware of customer needs; respond to demands in timely manner; aware of key business drivers; provides optimum service to clients; focus on customer satisfaction.
			diligence	demonstrate precision and accuracy in work; work in disciplined manner; demonstrate willingness to work hard; stay with tasks until completed, even when others give up
			efficiency	plan effectively; use time productively; be competent in performing tasks; be economical in use of resources or time; work in logical sequence; seek help; collaborate when appropriate
			reliability	act in a dependable, honest and trustworthy way; be loyal, authentic, and consistent in actions and relationships

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C			tenacity	stick to one's tasks achieving goals despite fatigue, frustration, failure and setbacks; meet personal commitments; demonstrates will to continue when work becomes difficult; goes above and beyond expectations; display firmness of character; demonstrate indomitable spirit; strive for excellence
			goal orientation	demonstrate strong ambition to successfully complete tasks; define strategies and plans effective for achieving the pursued objectives; give priority to actions that contribute to achieve pursued objectives; demonstrate focus on high performance and quality levels; seek continuous performance improvement
			patience	accept or tolerate delay, trouble or suffering without getting angry or upset; remain composed when faced with emotional or conflict situations; give people the space to make mistakes and learn from the experience
			resilience	handle challenges, disruption and change and recover from setbacks and adversity; tolerate and work constructively within unexpected, unpredictable and complex situations; stay calm and react in a constructive way to own or others' anger or when faced with obstacles or complaints; adapt to accommodate modifications in the workplace
D			leadership	guide, direct others to common goal by example and instruction; supervise, motivate and plan work for employees or teams; create and enforce time schedules, goals, metrics to maximise output; trust colleagues; work collaboratively with team mates; delegate within capability, responsibility parameters
			coaching	teach, guide others to act effectively, empathize; suggest optimum course of action; demonstrate and model best practice; guide by provision of relevant knowledge and support; prescribe exercises, drills to reinforce learning; acknowledge, praise, reward good practice and competence mastery
			conflict resolution	identify, prevent conflict; be diplomatic, sensitive; intervene, resolve conflicts or disputes in, proactive, peaceful manner; reduce negative impact of conflict; promote positive outcomes; create restorative working environment
			entrepreneurship	act upon ideas and opportunities to transform them, over time, into cultural, financial or social value for others
			manage quality	promote excellence in workplace processes, activities, deliverables; give relevant, constructive feedback on processes, products; establish procedures to prevent errors; pose appropriate questions to elicit accurate information for a purpose; encourage efficient, effective work practices; appraise, modify behaviour, performance

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			<p>motivate others</p> <p>get to know what drives and stimulates individuals to achieve goals and personal growth; demonstrate self-motivation and professionalism to inspire people; set realistic goals; engage in transparent planning of work with a clear division of tasks; ensure people understand how their role contributes to achieving corporate goals; encourage people by showing you appreciate their efforts and praising them for good work done; demonstrate people they have your trust; listen attentively and value other people's opinion; empower people to play a more active role in an organisation</p>
			<p>strategic thinking</p> <p>shape a vision for the future and be able to translate it into concrete ideas and plans; prepare strategies and come up with ideas and plans that can cope with changing environments and various challenges ahead; formulate achievable and cost-effective plans that address organisational goals and strategies; communicate a clear, vivid and relevant description or picture of where the organisation should be 3, 5 or 10 years</p>
E			<p>communication</p> <p>Effectively exchange information and ideas through verbal, non-verbal, visual and written means with others; alter communication style for different situations, people and mediums; listen to understand; clarify understanding; take different viewpoints into consideration</p>
			<p>negotiation</p> <p>communicate with others to reach a suitable outcome for all; build a common understanding; resolve a point of difference; stay focused on own and others' intentions or goals; demonstrate willingness to compromise; apply active listening to understand other's intentions or goals; build and adapt argumentation according to changing circumstances to improve chances for win-win solution</p>
			<p>networking</p> <p>Reach out to and meet up with people in a professional context; build a web of personal professional contacts; stay in touch with contacts with common interests and at influential positions in organisations; return favours; be open to help others without expecting to get something back</p>
			<p>teamwork</p> <p>work confidently within a group, assuming relevant role, to achieve both personal and collective goals; balance own contribution and success against others for benefit of the team; share the workload appropriately; recognise the value of other people's contributions and ideas; recognise and respect the role of others; support division or co-ownership of responsibilities</p>
F			<p>creativity</p> <p>suggest new ways of doing things; improvise, experiment confidently; be inspired by novelty; leverage experience for guidance; is in awe of new disciplines, topics; actively seek out, explore new areas; be curious, open-minded</p>
			<p>critical thinking</p> <p>ask appropriate questions to elicit quality information for a purpose; interpret information in context; be aware of "fake News" phenomenon"; appraise, analyse scenarios; exercise situational judgement</p>
			<p>decision making</p> <p>weigh pros and cons in balanced way; reason logically; deductive; deliberate over arguments; exercise judgement based on situation, evidence, empathy; be pragmatic</p>

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			initiative	act without direction; is conscientious, motivated to innovate, invent; is energetic, dynamic in approach to tasks, routines; proceed in entrepreneurial fashion; approaches tasks, challenges proactively; is courageous; continuously seek new and challenging opportunities; take risks
			problem-solving	reason inductively, deductively; use systems thinking; analyse, evaluate alternative solutions; plan, conduct investigations; interpret information; draw conclusions; make decisions based on best analysis
G			ethical behaviour	act according to accepted principles of right and wrong; apply criteria of fairness, transparency and impartiality, in work practices, when dealing with people; respect human rights; be generous; honest; act with empathy; be socially oriented; act according to honourable principles
			respect privacy	be aware of high-level provisions of GDPR; recognise the right to keep personal information private; respect, protect personal data; disclose personal information only to authorised people; be discreet; inform others of rights to privacy
			respect for diversity	respect different cultural, social and sexual affinities; respond inclusively, equitably to all; actively promote social justice, confront discrimination in the workplace and society
			respect the environment	respect home, workplace, neighbourhood environment proactively; show interest in nature, conservation, ecology; model positive environmental behaviour; enact environmentally friendly principles, policies, regulations in the workplace; promote environmental sustainability in society
0	Legal and financial literacy	0.1	Managing budgets or finances	determining the distribution and availability financial assets and putting in place financial and administrative controls
		0.2	identify legal requirements	conduct research for applicable legal and normative procedures and standards, analyse and derive legal requirements that apply to the organisation, its policies and products.
1	Information and data literacy	1.1	Browsing, searching and filtering data, information and digital content	To articulate information needs, to search for data, information and content in digital environments, to access them and to navigate between them. To create and update personal search strategies.
		1.2	Evaluating data, information and digital content	To analyse, compare and critically evaluate the credibility and reliability of sources of data, information and digital content. To analyse, interpret and critically evaluate the data, information and digital content.
		1.3	Managing data, information and digital content	To organise, store and retrieve data, information, and content in digital environments. To organise and process them in a structured environment.

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2	Communication and collaboration	2.1	Interacting through digital technologies	To interact through a variety of digital technologies and to understand appropriate digital communication means for a given context.
		2.2	Sharing through digital technologies	To share data, information and digital content with others through appropriate digital technologies. To act as an intermediary, to know about referencing and attribution practices.
		2.3	Engaging citizenship through digital technologies	To participate in society through the use of public and private digital services. To seek opportunities for self-empowerment and for participatory citizenship through appropriate digital technologies.
		2.4	Collaborating through digital technologies	To use digital tools and technologies for collaborative processes, and for co-construction and co-creation of data, resources and knowledge.
		2.5	Netiquette	To be aware of behavioural norms and know-how while using digital technologies and interacting in digital environments. To adapt communication strategies to the specific audience and to be aware of cultural and generational diversity in digital environments.
		2.6	Managing digital identity	To create, and manage one or multiple digital identities, to be able to protect one's own reputation, to deal with the data that one produces through several digital tools, environments and services.
3	Digital content creation	3.1	Developing digital content	To create and edit digital content in different formats, to express oneself through digital means.
		3.2	Integrating and re-elaborating digital content	To modify, refine and integrate new information and content into an existing body of knowledge and resources to create new, original and relevant content and knowledge.
		3.3	Copyright and licences	To understand how copyright and licences apply to digital information and content.
		3.4	Programming	To plan and develop a sequence of understandable instructions for a computing system to solve a given problem or to perform a specific task.
4	Safety	4.1	Protecting devices	To protect devices and digital content, and to understand risks and threats in digital environments. To know about safety and security measures and to have a due regard to reliability and privacy.
		4.2	Protecting personal data and privacy	To protect personal data and privacy in digital environments. To understand how to use and share personally identifiable information while being able to protect oneself and others from damages. To understand that digital services use a "Privacy policy" to inform how personal data is used.

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		4.3	Protecting health and well-being	To be able to avoid health-risks and threats to physical and psychological well-being while using digital technologies. To be able to protect oneself and others from possible dangers in digital environments (e.g. cyber bullying). To be aware of digital technologies for social well-being and social inclusion.
		4.4	Protecting the environment	To be aware of the environmental impact of digital technologies and their use.
5	Problem solving	5.1	Solving technical problems	To identify technical problems when operating devices and using digital environments, and to solve them (from troubleshooting to solving more complex problems).
		5.2	Identifying needs and technological responses	To assess needs and to identify, evaluate, select and use digital tools and possible technological responses and to solve them. To adjust and customise digital environments to personal needs (e.g. accessibility).
		5.3	Creatively using digital technology	To use digital tools and technologies to create knowledge and to innovate processes and products. To engage individually and collectively in cognitive processing to understand and resolve conceptual problems and problem situations in digital environments.
		5.4	Identifying digital competence gaps	To understand where one's own digital competence needs to be improved or updated. To be able to support others with their digital competence development. To seek opportunities for self-development and to keep up to date with the digital evolution.

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Mapping of other EU Frameworks to the ETF.

Lifecomp			ETF	Matching
Personal area			ETF	Matching
P1	self-regulation	awareness and management of emotions, thoughts and behaviour	self-control	<i>definition</i>
P2	flexibility	ability to manage transitions and uncertainty, and to face challenges	adaptability	<i>definition</i>
P3	wellbeing	pursuit of life satisfaction, care of physical, mental and social health, and adoption of a sustainable lifestyle	respect the environment	<i>definition</i>
			self-management	<i>definition + BZ</i>
Social area			ETF	Matching
S1	empathy	the understanding of another person's emotions, experiences and values, and the provision of appropriate responses	respect for diversity	<i>BZ</i>
S2	communication	use of relevant communication strategies, domain-specific codes and tools depending on the context and the content	communication	<i>definition</i>
S3	collaboration	engagement in group activity and teamwork acknowledging and respecting others	teamwork	<i>definition + BZ</i>
Learning to learn area			ETF	Matching
L1	growth mindset	belief in one's and others' potential to continuously learn and progress	personal development	<i>definition + BZ</i>
			positive attitude	<i>definition + BZ</i>
L2	critical thinking	assessment of information and arguments to support reasoned conclusions and develop innovative solutions	critical thinking	<i>definition</i>
L3	managing learning	the planning, organising, monitoring and reviewing of one's own learning	personal development	<i>definition + BZ</i>
Greencomp				
Embodying sustainability values			ETF	Matching
1.1	Valuing sustainability	To reflect on personal values; identify and explain how values vary among people and over time, while critically evaluating how they align with sustainability values.	respect the environment	<i>definition</i>
1.2	Supporting fairness	To support equity and justice for current and future generations and learn from previous generations for sustainability.	ethical behaviour	<i>definition + BZ</i>
1.3	Promoting nature	To acknowledge that humans are part of nature; and to respect the needs and rights of other species and of nature itself in order to restore and regenerate healthy and resilient ecosystems.	respect the environment	<i>definition</i>

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Embracing complexity in sustainability			ETF	Matching
2.1	Systems thinking	To approach a sustainability problem from all sides; to consider time, space and context in order to understand how elements interact within and between systems.	strategic thinking	<i>definition + BZ</i>
2.2	Critical thinking	To assess information and arguments, identify assumptions, challenge the status quo, and reflect on how personal, social and cultural backgrounds influence thinking and conclusions.	critical thinking	<i>definition</i>
2.3	Problem framing	To formulate current or potential challenges as a sustainability problem in terms of difficulty, people involved, time and geographical scope, in order to identify suitable approaches to anticipating and preventing problems, and to mitigating and adapting to already existing problems.	problem-solving	<i>definition</i>
Envisioning sustainable futures			ETF	Matching
3.1	Futures literacy	To envision alternative sustainable futures by imagining and developing alternative scenarios and identifying the steps needed to achieve a preferred sustainable future	creativity	<i>definition</i>
3.2	Adaptability	To manage transitions and challenges in complex sustainability situations and make decisions related to the future in the face of uncertainty, ambiguity and risk	adaptability	<i>definition</i>
3.3	Exploratory thinking	To adopt a relational way of thinking by exploring and linking different disciplines, using creativity and experimentation with novel ideas or methods	creativity	<i>definition</i>
Acting for sustainability			ETF	Matching
4.1	Political agency	To navigate the political system, identify political responsibility and accountability for unsustainable behaviour, and demand effective policies for sustainability	NA	
4.2	Collective action	To act for change in collaboration with others	teamwork	<i>definition</i>
4.3	Individual initiative	To identify own potential for sustainability and to actively contribute to improving prospects for the community and the planet	initiative	<i>definition</i>

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EntreComp				
Ideas & Opportunities			ETF	Matching
1.1	Spotting opportunities	Use your imagination and abilities to identify opportunities for creating value		<i>definition</i>
1.2	Creativity	Develop creative and purposeful ideas	creativity	<i>definition</i>
1.3	Vision	Work towards your vision of the future	creativity	<i>definition</i>
1.4	Valuing ideas	Make the most of ideas and opportunities	entrepreneurship	<i>definition</i>
1.5	Ethical and sustainable thinking	Assess the consequences and impact of ideas, opportunities and actions	ethical behaviour	<i>definition</i>
			respect the environment	<i>definition</i>
Resources			ETF	Matching
2.1	Self-awareness and self-efficacy	Believe in yourself and keep developing	self-management	<i>definition</i>
2.2	Motivation and perseverance	Stay focused and don't give up	tenacity	<i>definition</i>
			resilience	<i>definition</i>
			patience	<i>definition</i>
2.3	Mobilising resources	Gather and manage the resources you need	organisation	<i>Definition + BZ</i>
2.4	Financial and economic literacy	Develop financial and economic know how	financial and legal literacy	<i>definition</i>

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2.5	Mobilising others	Inspire, enthuse and get others on board	motivate others	<i>definition</i>
Into action			ETF	Matching
3.1	Taking the initiative	Go for it	initiative	<i>definition</i>
3.2	Planning and management	Prioritize, organise and follow-up	adaptability	<i>definition</i>
3.3	Coping with uncertainty, ambiguity and risk	Make decisions dealing with uncertainty, ambiguity and risk	strategic thinking	<i>definition</i>
3.4	Working with others	Team up, collaborate and network	teamwork	<i>definition</i>
			networking	<i>definition</i>
3.5	Learning through experience	Learn by doing	personal development	<i>definition</i>

Keywords and terms associated to each of the skills of the Skills Match Framework.

Behavioural skill	Description
accountability	perform, complete assigned tasks in a goal-oriented manner; take ownership; accept liability for professional decisions, involving self or others; realise that choices and actions have positive and negative consequences; recognise limits to autonomy; understand when to seek help
adaptability	demonstrate openness to change when faced with changing demands and circumstances; adjust plans, goals, behaviours and actions to effectively and successfully cope with change; demonstrate flexibility when coping with various circumstances
coaching	teach, guide others to act effectively, empathize; suggest optimum course of action; demonstrate and model best practice; guide by provision of relevant knowledge and support; prescribe exercises, drills to reinforce learning; acknowledge, praise, reward good practice and competence mastery
communication	Effectively exchange information and ideas through verbal, non-verbal, visual and written means with others; alter communication style for different situations, people and mediums; listen to understand; clarify understanding; take different viewpoints into consideration
conflict resolution	identify, prevent conflict; be diplomatic, sensitive; intervene, resolve conflicts or disputes in, proactive, peaceful manner; reduce negative impact of conflict; promote positive outcomes; create restorative working environment
creativity	suggest new ways of doing things; improvise, experiment confidently; be inspired by novelty; leverage experience for guidance; is in awe of new disciplines, topics; actively seek out, explore new areas; be curious, open-minded
critical thinking	ask appropriate questions to elicit quality information for a purpose; interpret information in context; be aware of "fake News" phenomenon"; appraise, analyse scenarios; exercise situational judgement
customer focus	aware of customer needs; respond to demands in timely manner; aware of key business drivers; provides optimum service to clients; focus on customer satisfaction.
decision making	weigh pros and cons in balanced way; reason logically; deductive; deliberate over arguments; exercise judgement based on situation, evidence, empathy; be pragmatic
diligence	demonstrate precision and accuracy in work; work in disciplined manner; demonstrate willingness to work hard; stay with tasks until completed, even when others give up
efficiency	plan effectively; use time productively; be competent in performing tasks; be economical in use of resources or time; work in logical sequence; seek help; collaborate when appropriate
entrepreneurship	act upon ideas and opportunities to transform them, over time, into cultural, financial or social value for others
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	principles
goal orientation	demonstrate strong ambition to successfully complete tasks; define strategies and plans effective for achieving the pursued objectives; give priority to actions that contribute to achieve pursued objectives; demonstrate focus on high performance and quality levels; seek continuous performance improvement
initiative	act without direction; is conscientious, motivated to innovate, invent; is energetic, dynamic in approach to tasks, routines; proceed in entrepreneurial fashion; approaches tasks, challenges proactively; is courageous; continuously seek new and challenging opportunities; take risks
leadership	guide, direct others to common goal by example and instruction; supervise, motivate and plan work for employees or teams; create and enforce time schedules, goals, metrics to maximise output; trust colleagues; work collaboratively with team mates; delegate within capability, responsibility parameters
manage quality	promote excellence in workplace processes, activities, deliverables; give relevant, constructive feedback on processes, products; establish procedures to prevent errors; pose appropriate questions to elicit accurate information for a purpose; encourage efficient, effective work practices; appraise, modify behaviour, performance
motivate others	get to know what drives and stimulates individuals to achieve goals and personal growth; demonstrate self-motivation and professionalism to inspire people; set realistic goals; engage in transparent planning of work with a clear division of tasks; ensure people understand how their role contributes to achieving corporate goals; encourage people by showing you appreciate their efforts and praising them for good work done; demonstrate people they have your trust; listen attentively and value other people's opinion; empower people to play a more active role in an organisation
motivation	the drive to perform a task and achieve results with enthusiasm, determination and autonomy; do what needs to be done, without influence from other people; find a reason and strength to complete a task, even when challenging, without giving up or needing others to encourage them
negotiation	communicate with others to reach a suitable outcome for all; build a common understanding; resolve a point of difference; stay focused on own and others' intentions or goals; demonstrate willingness to compromise; apply active listening to understand other's intentions or goals; build and adapt argumentation according to changing circumstances to improve chances for win-win solution
networking	Reach out to and meet up with people in a professional context; build a web of personal professional contacts; stay in touch with contacts with common interests and at influential positions in organisations; return favours; be open to help others without expecting to get something back
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tenacity	stick to one's tasks achieving goals despite fatigue, frustration, failure and setbacks; meet personal commitments; demonstrates will to continue when work becomes difficult; goes above and beyond expectations; display firmness of character; demonstrate indomitable spirit; strive for excellence

